

Emergency Management and Response through 3D Maps and Novel Geo-Information Sources

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Abstract. Geographical Information Systems (GIS) are essential when representing the Common Operational Picture to have a complete understanding of the situation in disasters. A three-dimensional (3D) representation of the terrain, buildings and surroundings of an emergency area increases the situational awareness of first responders in comparison to the classical 2D map representation when facing the emergency response. This paper describes the architectural solution adopted and the set of functionalities developed to enable: a) timely geolocated representation of near real-time multi-sensor data from heterogeneous sources, b) interaction through a 3D GIS environment for virtual emergency area inspection, c) management of users, scenarios and geospatial elements, and d) advanced geospatial processes. Then, the components that enable the main geospatial capabilities are technically detailed. Finally, validation and evaluation activities carried out with professional first responders and trainees are described together with the results and feedback obtained.

Keywords: Emergency management · Disaster response · Command and control · Location based services.

1 Introduction

Maps are a useful means to support Emergency Management and Response (EMR). The shift from 2D to 3D maps represents a notable advancement, aiding first responders in comprehending the emergency environment, with an enhanced view. Including details like terrain slopes and building structures, offers a more comprehensive understanding of the situation. Moreover, novel sensing capabilities and data sources hold immense value in enhancing safety and response efficiency. Notably, cutting-edge tools with real-time indoor and outdoor geolocation and geosensing capabilities are reaching the market. Leveraging these tools, however, poses challenges in dealing with substantial volumes of diverse positioning records, demanding efficient processing, storage, representation, and exploitation techniques. Overcoming these challenges will help maximise the potential benefits of these technological advancements.

First Responders handling disaster response may benefit of advanced Command and Control (CC) solutions that rely on 3D Geographical Information System capabilities. Therefore, the present paper aims to describe the architecture and technology stack chosen to create a 2D/3D geospatial data management solution providing a set of key functionalities in a Command and Control centre during emergency response, extending a previous conference paper [15]. Two main novel additional contributions are presented in this paper. Firstly, the description of technical aspects of the geospatial data management architecture to accommodate new functionalities such as consulting elevation profiles for given routes, visualisation of point clouds and orthophotos have been included. Secondly, the methodology and results of two hands-on activities with first responders are depicted in order to validate the tool in relevant scenarios.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes previous works addressing the problem in the literature and Section 3 describes the proposed architecture and functionalities. Then, Section 4 and 5 present performance measurements and the validation with end users respectively, followed by the discussion and description of future work in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 presents the conclusions.

2 Related work

Diverse first responders collaborate in EMR, each with unique roles and backgrounds. The information must be presented in a comprehensible manner to enhance the decision-making process. Geographical Information Systems (GIS) technology has been shown to be of great help in multiple ways and in various situations such as earthquakes, wildfires, dust storms, health hazards, and terrorism [11]. Based on GIS technology and maps, spatial analysis capabilities support managing the risk and solving the mapping and assessment of hazards, for example, identifying high-hazard regions within given vicinity. It is also interesting in that it provides visual models that help decision-makers make the best use of these advancements.

The interest and preference of end users towards three-dimensional (3D) maps is high, and the study of natural dangers and disasters in 3D has grown significantly during the past few years. 3D maps have the potential to improve the disaster management process according to some authors, since they resolve many perception problems and provide more clearly presented information [13]. User interviews in that study confirmed that young people prefer 3D information. Another study with 71 users concluded that 3D visualisation was considered important by 62% of the users; a rather high result considering that half were not familiar with GIS technology [33].

Enabling 3D navigation for rescuers in unknown indoor and outdoor environments, thanks to accurate 3D positioning, simplifies the logistics of emergency operations [34], [24]. Some works have focused on the use of images from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for 3D modelling. 3D reconstruction of the scene has been proven as a crucial aspect for efficient management of search and rescue

efforts [31], [27]. Exploiting different heterogeneous sources such as geolocated security cameras and their field of view has also been a topic for other research works [20]. Therefore, supporting 3D maps in the Command and Control Centre, with real-time location information visualisation and analysis is very relevant. Some authors stress, however, that most traditional disaster management systems do not incorporate support for multiple emerging data sources, while the need for real-time big data processing tools that can provide swift and precise outcomes remains unaddressed [29].

In this sense, the availability of geo-information including 3D models of built infrastructures and buildings is becoming common. In addition, diverse up-to-date data with geospatial nature is generated by the most advanced technologies. With the advent of location-based sensors and smartphones equipped with GNSS, the real-time location of First Responders deployed in the field can be monitored. Moreover, satellite and airborne sensors as well as fully fledged Earth Observation solutions such as the Copernicus Emergency Management Service [23] offer large-scale geo-referenced optical, multispectral or Synthetic Aperture Radar [17] imagery for from-above views of disaster areas, while geolocated cameras, sensors and even Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) scanners mounted on robots and utility vehicles help inspect and assess the emergency situation from the ground. Combining these potential sources requires robust tools that support geospatial data analysis over time through interactive visualisation.

The exchange and integration of 3D models, point clouds and datasets with 2D spatial data resources, however, is not straightforward. Thus, the definition and usage of standards are important. Some model formats are proprietary, while others have been developed by international standardisation organisations and come from the CAD/BIM, GIS, or Web domains. Both well established and very recent standards for different purposes are found. For instance, the Web Map Service (WMS) is a specification developed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), that has also become an ISO standard [22], for serving georeferenced map images over the Internet. These images are typically produced by a map server from data provided by a GIS database. At the same time, 3D Tiles is another OGC open standard for massive heterogeneous 3D geospatial datasets such as point clouds, buildings, photogrammetry, and vector data [9]. Substantial efforts to improve interoperability between domains are found in the literature and newly proposed standards such as CityGML 3.0 have the potential to impact integration, between BIM and GIS for instance [30].

Some well-known software solutions implement these and other standards. For instance, Geoserver [21], an open source map server for sharing geospatial data used in some emergency management applications (such as [25]), implements WMS, Web Feature Service (WFS) Web Coverage Service (WCS), and additional protocols like Web Processing Service (WPS) through available extensions. CesiumJS is an open platform that implements 3D Tiles and uses the map engine of WebGL to provide multi-dimensional earth and real terrain display [10]. Some recent works have used this platform for representing virtual situations for urban road emergency training [18]. However, to the authors' knowledge, no

other works have presented a platform architecture to be used during emergency response, ready for being integrated with additional data sources in real-time.

3 Solution description

3.1 Architecture and components

The solution is formed of a Command and Control (CC) web application, a set of databases, a map serving tool, a set of multiple purpose GIS servers (pointcloud, terrain and elevation) and an API server that hosts the business logic offering the functionalities on top of the emergency database to the web application (Fig. 1). In addition, a set of auxiliary tools and components support other tasks such as user authentication and interaction with external data sources. The proposed solution also includes two client applications relying on augmented reality to offer the first responders deployed in the field an enhanced understanding of their surroundings (for smartphones and smart see-through glasses).

Fig. 1. Architecture diagram of the technology stack.

CC Web App interface : The proposed solution is a web-based Command and Control application with geospatial visualisation and geocomputation capabilities. Its main objectives are the representation of the area of the scenario and real-time visualisation of the spatial types of data of elements (First Responders, sensors and geolocated resources and risks) that are taking part. Data are obtained from third-party tools that are able to sense, monitor and observe the

disaster area from multiple perspectives through different technologies and are made accessible for applications such as the CC Web App interface.

The application includes user management capabilities and emergency inventory management. Two main frameworks have been used to build the application, which are:

- JHipster [28]: Open source development platform to generate, develop and deploy web applications and microservices.
- CesiumJS [10]: Open source javascript library for creating 3D globes and maps. Its main strength is the 3D geospatial visualisation.

Geoserver and multi-purpose GIS servers : Geoserver [21] is a well-known open-source server for sharing geospatial data. It also has geocomputation capabilities. Geoserver implements OGC protocols such as Web Feature Service (WFS), Web Map Service (WMS) or Web Processing Service (WPS) and has been selected as the main map-serving tool for the web-based application. The base map layer contents that are served by Geoserver have been obtained from OpenStreetMap [14]. Geoserver is also used for heatmaps representation and emergency centroid calculation. This centroid is calculated based on all the elements associated with an emergency and is used to centre the map when loaded.

Three additional GIS servers are used: a point cloud server for 3D Tiles, a 3D terrain server, and an elevation server for querying and retrieving elevation data from Digital Elevation Model files.

Relational databases : The architecture involves one main relational database, the Emergency database, which persists the real-time and historical information of the evolution of the disaster response. Other databases are used for user authentication and for the storage of map base layers information. Postgres [26] was selected for these databases, with the PostGIS extension. This extension is not needed for the authentication database.

API server : The main business logic of the emergency management is provided by an API server consisting of a set of REST API methods, working on top of the Emergency database, developed in Java Spring Boot [32]. The API server interacts with the elevation server module to obtain the elevation above the sea level of a given pair of geo-coordinates.

Smartphone/Smart glasses augmented reality client applications : The CC WebApp interface is complemented with two client application versions for the first responders deployed in the field. They use augmented reality to represent information of the relative location and distance to other first responders, their risk situation and the relative location and distance of georeferenced elements of interest [12].

3.2 Interfaces and input data from other tools

Data from different sources are received from a middleware system, also developed in the research project but out of the scope of this paper. This system is in charge of the management and fusion of multiple data sources such as sensor information from wearables or drones. It is a bundle of software services with functionalities for data source management and secure data flow among others. The API service developed includes a specific endpoint for each data source and acts as a consumer of this middleware so that the received information can be exploited and persisted in a structured manner.

Apart from this middleware system, a Kafka broker for asynchronous messaging interacts with a websocket used by the CC WebApp to represent received alerts in real-time in the web user interface.

3.3 Main functionalities provided

After describing the main components in the previous section, the main functionalities that the CC solution provides are described in the following.

User management : The concept of user management describes the ability of administrators to manage and configure user access to different IT resources such as services, applications or systems. It is a key concept that enables security and controls who is able to access what information or service. A CC application requires a secure access to handle and interact with all the information and functionalities. This access is granted by the use of user-based authentication.

Scenario management : The same Command and Control application hosted in a server or an on-premise deployment can be used, in general, to operate in different emergencies and geographical areas. This can occur in different time frames or simultaneously. Therefore, having ways to separate the scenarios is a useful capability. The management of the emergency scenario involves multiple stages in order to setup all the configuration and device resources that need to be associated to the corresponding first responders.

- Creation of a new setting. The concept of "setting" stands for an area where many emergencies can be added. A setting can be, for instance, a country, a state or a city.
- Creation of a new first responder
- Creation of a new emergency. Location, start date and first responders can be specified among other fields.
- Edition of an emergency
- Save a new device
- User configuration where an application user can be assigned to a first responder.
- Adding or removing associations between first responders and devices they may carry or wear.

The creation of a new setting is enabled if separate geographical areas are expected to be covered by a unique deployment of the CC application. This enables the association of each geographical area with the available maps.

Fig. 2. Emergency Dashboard to select an emergency [15].

Inside a setting, multiple emergencies can be covered simultaneously. Each emergency is focused on a more specific geographical area specified by the limits of a bounding box. Running emergencies are marked as “active” but finished ones and the associated information recorded are persisted for future post-emergency studies. The Emergency Dashboard, Fig. 2, visualises a screenshot of the geographical area map and basic information of each created emergency, and they can be filtered by Scenarios. When any of these emergencies is selected, the application enters in 3D map visualisation view.

Resource and device configuration : Multiple and heterogeneous types of resources are usually used in an emergency operation. For instance, first responders are personal resources. In each emergency, a list of first responders is assigned. Other types of resources can be vehicles, tools, machinery, sensors or other equipment. Sometimes these resources need to be associated to a given first responder. For instance, the information coming from a wearable sensor must be linked to a specific first responder.

Many of the tools developed in the current research project are resources that provide different kinds of data, shared through a common data middleware. This information is represented in the CC application if the correct IDs are associated to the first responder, for instance, if the sensor is providing the health status or positioning of the first responder. However, not all devices need always to be attached to a first responder. We address the following resources or devices providing data: a) Video sources: streaming video from sources like thermal

cameras will need to be configured in order to have access to their incoming contents; b) Drones; c) Wearables.

This association between a first responder and a device needs to be done by emergency, since from one emergency to another the personal resources and the devices they will be using could rotate.

Layered 2D, 3D maps and road network information : Geospatial base layers are key to represent the geographical context where the emergency operation occurs. In summary, a map layer is a GIS component containing groups of points, lines or polygon features that represent real-world entities, or images (like satellite imagery). They help locating what is happening, and where the personnel and technical resources are in relation to other points of interest.

These kinds of layers are provided through Geoserver, the selected open source standalone GIS server which provides the main OGC capabilities to work with 2D spatial tiles in an interoperable way, on top of a PostGIS relational database server. To construct the base 2D maps, contents have been downloaded from OpenStreetMap, and prepared to be served through Geoserver in the form of tiles. The road network information is also extracted from OpenStreetMap and incorporated to the PostGIS database so that Geoserver can also serve it.

With current availability of satellite imagery, a realistic view of the scenario can be offered to the first responders with orthophotos (Fig. 3). Having the capability of showing aerial photographs or satellite imagery can be of much help for situational awareness better understanding the type of terrain, the existence of vegetation, roads or buildings. Orthophotos can be incorporated to the CC solution by using third party online WMS services or by downloading the data and self-hosting it through Geoserver.

Fig. 3. Representation of orthophoto layer [7].

The 3D terrain capabilities are a significant part of the proposed solution. To enable this 3D terrain, a DEM (Digital Elevation Model) of the area to be represented is required. This file is processed in order to create tiles and these are served using the OGC standard Web Map Service (WMS).

Apart from the 3D terrain, the visualisation of point clouds has been included in the solution to enhance emergency perception. Point clouds captured from LiDAR sensors, Fig. 4, give a unique 3D perception of the environment. Fig. 5 depicts a combined view of the 3D terrain with orthophoto layers and a representation LiDAR point clouds obtained from a mobile mapping vehicle. In a disaster, machinery equipped with these sensors may be able to inspect the area of interest together with other more traditional sensors such as cameras. Visualizing the reconstruction provided by the point cloud from the CC centre in real-time can help first responders know the situation of the scenario beforehand and evaluate risks and damages prior to sending personal effectives.

Fig. 4. Representation of point cloud data [1] on top of OpenStreetMap data [6].

Offline mode: 2D and 3D layers can usually be obtained through third party map service providers, and this is a very usual approach in software applications using maps. But this requires a constant connection to their remote servers. It is quite usual that during an emergency, the access to internet is limited or completely lost. And only a private local network is available to ensure communication among first responders and the emergency management tools. Using self-hosted services such as Geoserver instead of relying on external map providers, the lack of internet connection during the critical situation does not restrict the map usage.

First responder localisation and tracking : This capability enables displaying the position of a first responder over a digital map and see their positions

Fig. 5. Representation examples of 3D terrain elevation with orthophoto imagery [7] as base layer and LiDAR pointcloud from mobile mapping [1]

change over time. It is key to ensure the Command and Control operators know where first responders in the field are, with an acceptable delay and an acceptable precision in space. The accuracy of the positioning will strongly depend on the device providing that data, but the Command and Control application will need ensure that it is represented using the correct spatial referencing system. The information of all the geolocated first responders is shown on 2D or 3D maps according to their real-time location, following established refresh-rates, which can be fixed or personalised by each user.

Capabilities for outdoor and indoor localisation are provided by the CC application, for instance, enabling 3D representations of buildings and the location of the first responders at different levels. CesiumJS includes the possibility of representing polygons. For indoor locations of first responders or casualties, buildings can be represented as simple extruded polygons or as specific 3D models created on purpose.

Route calculation : Route calculation is a functionality that helps obtain an optimal path to reach a final objective position from a given initial position. This optimal path is usually computed as the path that implies the lowest cost. The most common ways of quantifying this cost are distance and travel time. Multiple well-known algorithms exist to obtain optimal or near-optimal results (sometimes a compromise must be found because the computation time to get the best result might be excessive). In general, the input for these algorithms is a set of ways and nodes, modelled as a graph. Having the road network imported as a graph is of high importance in order to be able to compute the shortest paths by using algorithms like Dijkstra [16] and A* [19]. The CC application enables the calculation of the shortest path between two locations. Currently, the changes of the road network due to an incident are not supported but this is

a functionality envisioned for the future roadmap of the tool. After requesting a route between two first responders, the computed path is printed on the map, and distance and duration information are displayed.

Elevation profile : Emergencies sometimes happen in hard-to-reach areas like mountains, forests or neighbourhoods with high slopes. Vehicles or machinery may have problems accessing these areas. Therefore, predefining the intended path and assessing the terrain elevation profile provides valuable information that helps decision-making. This functionality permits a user to draw a path as a sequence of consecutive points on the web application map (following the route path provided by the previous functionality or not) and request the system to compute and display the elevation profile, as shown in Fig. 6. Besides that, when clicking the graphic, the following additional metrics are calculated and shown in the web application: maximum uphill and downhill gradients, percentage of route with uphill gradient, average uphill gradient, percentage of route considered flat (elevation between -3% and 3%), average flat gradient, percentage of route with downhill gradient, average downhill gradient, and a 2D plot of the elevation profile.

Fig. 6. Calculated elevation profile of a route.

Cataloging and location of necessary equipment and geospatial elements : The CC application supports the creation of geospatial elements of interest by drawing them on a map. These can be generic “POINT”, “LINE” or “POLYGON” shape types of elements. This allows displaying them on the map in client applications carried by first responders in the field. For instance,

the Inventory creation functionality provided by the CC application acts as an authoring tool that creates geospatial entities that are then displayed within the assigned emergency, and can be used by any other application that uses the API, such as the augmented reality smartphone and see-through glasses clients. In addition to the shape type, currently, the elements can be categorised into Resources, Citizens in Risk, Danger Area, Alerts or Mobile Command and Control Centre location. The user is able to draw the element on the map and it is then saved in the system with associated details.

Real-time environmental and first responders' health status through sensor data visualisation : Via third party tools, the data collected by multiple wearable sensors and centralised by the data logger are shared through the middleware system. This information gives valuable insights of the situation of the first responders' safety, apart from the localisation data that has previously been addressed. In addition, it enables quickly alerting the commanders to a potentially injured FR and it provides actionable intelligence without needing audio or visual communication between the FR and their commander.

Drone Flight plan and telemetry visualisation : Drones are another key part of emergency management nowadays. These are very valuable resources that help operations from an aerial perspective. Integrating their information in Command and Control applications is very useful. In the proposed solution, via the middleware system, telemetry information of the drones are shared with the Command and Control application in order to display their status and position in real time. For instance, the CC application is capable of displaying and updating the position with a given refresh rate. The main purpose of this functionality is not handling the flight mission, which needs a very frequent and critical monitoring to guarantee the safety of the UAV and the personnel involved but following their approximate situation in context with the rest of the elements and resources being part of the emergency operation. In Fig. 7, the position and details of a flying drone are represented on the map. Since the CC application allows 3D visualisation of the scene, apart from the 2D positions, the elevation can be represented. Moreover, showing or hiding the expected flight plan is enabled.

Alerts : The management of alerts is key to allow acting fast and efficiently in decision-making. This is valid for first responders in the Command and Control Centre and for the ones deployed in the field. Displaying alerts that require attention from a responsible at the Command and Control Centre is an important functionality. In general, alerts are expected to be shared through the middleware system. In addition, a specific component enables subscription to Common Alerting Protocol servers provided by authorised entities.

Fig. 7. Flying drone details with activated visualisation of the flight plan [15].

Post-Emergency functionalities : The post-emergency management of the collected information helps to understand and evaluate the emergency response, once finished. The following functionalities are given:

- Statistics dashboards: Interactive charts and tables about statistics of alarms, numbers of exchanged messages, number of injured people treated.
- Reporting: Creation of summary reports about the evolution of the emergency from the beginning to the end.
- Geospatial statistics: This helps understanding the movements of first responders in the field, extracting quantitative data about areas visited, distances they have traveled, time to reach some locations, time they have spent in a dangerous zone, and so on. Visual representations such as charts and heatmaps are used (Fig. 8).

3.4 Technical description

Even though the web application provides generalistic user administration and accounts-related functionalities, the main technical particularities belong to functions involving the visual components that show the emergency dashboard, the components that enable the user interaction to create new shapes associated with an emergency and all the components that allow 3D geospatial visualisation and interaction capabilities. In the following, we describe their technical considerations.

Cesium as the core GIS component : The main web interface component is where the emergency map and information are embedded in the website, using Cesium.JS, an open source javascript library for creating 3D globes and maps.

Fig. 8. Heatmap with positions from a selected first responder [15].

When an emergency is selected in the emergency dashboard, this component automatically loads. Cesium’s *WebMapServiceImageryProvider* function loads a base map for the world globe and a detailed map of the emergency setting from Geoserver. In the process of loading the component, there are three types of API requests that are invoked to retrieve emergency-associated data: 1) calls made only once, when the component loads, 2) calls made when the component loads and whenever the information is updated and 3) calls made when the operator selects a specific entity on the map.

Once the main component has loaded and the initial information has been retrieved from the API, the first operation that is done is an initial camera flight to the centre of the bounding rectangle of the emergency. For this operation, Cesium’s *CameraFlyTo* function is used and the coordinates are obtained from an API call that computes the minimum bounding box that covers the last positions of all the geolocated elements in the selected emergency.

The World globe, map layers and emergency entities are visualised using Cesium’s Viewer component. Any Cesium function has to be inside this component. Cesium has different kind of components for visualizing Entities. The ones used in this application are the following:

- *ModelGraphics*: loads 3D models in glTF format (drones, buildings, ...).
- *PolylineGraphics*: used for representing drone flight plan, line shape of interest, and route information.
- *BillboardGraphics*: loads an image representing a first responder type or any other point as a shape of interest.
- *LabelGraphics*: used for showing a first responder’s code.
- *PolygonGraphics*: used for showing polygon shape of interest.
- *PointGraphics*: used for representing drone’s mission waypoints.
- *WallGraphics*: used for representing route elevation profile.

Using *WebMapServiceImageryProvider* as well, a heatmap layer of positions of first responders can be represented. This layer is created in Geoserver applying a transformation to a style.

For interaction with the 2D and 3D maps, the user can move the view in any direction and can select any entity displayed in the viewer. When an entity is selected, a description is shown with *EntityDescription* component. There is also a menu function called “Zoom to” where user can redirect the camera to any first responder or shape of interest in the emergency. Cesium’s *CameraFlyTo* function is used, as for the initial camera position. There is an specific component for creation of new shapes in the emergency. Cesium viewer’s 3D globe is loaded, and the user can select what emergency wants to work on. The user can manually draw point, line or polygon shapes in any place of the map, assign a category to the shape and save it. Cesium has a *ScreenSpaceEventHandler* function for managing user clicks over the Cesium Viewer. Once the new shapes are saved, they are included in the Emergency Database and can be visualised using the CC application or any other application that uses the API.

Geoserver map creation process and usage : The process for serving a map with Geoserver starts obtaining an OpenStreetMap file of the wanted area. This map has to be processed into a PostGIS database with Imposm tool [4]. Applying a specific mapping in Imposm, converts the map information into several database tables. Then, Geoserver allows to import these tables. Each one works as a layer in Geoserver. For visualizing a layer like a typical map, a specific style has to be applied to each layer. For the creation of the whole map, a custom selection of layers has been chosen. The desired layers must be grouped into a “layer group”. The order in which the layers are added when creating this group is important. Once the map is created, it is served to the CC application by WMS (Web Map Service) standard. Orthophoto layers are also served offline if needed. Even though they can be requested through existing third party WMS services, having them stored and served locally reduces dependency on internet connection. Imagery is, therefore, downloaded and self-hosted in Geoserver and visualised in Cesium as another map layer. In Geoserver, a new “store” of type Raster Data Source must be created with the orthophotos data previously stored in GeoTIFF format. Cesium’s *WebMapServiceImageryProvider* function loads the map as another 2D map.

Cesium-terrain-server preparation and usage : Apart from imagery layers for 2D maps, the solution includes 3D terrain layers that are supported by a specific separate GIS server. In our case, we import 3D terrain using *CesiumTerrainProvider* function. Cesium accepts heightmap or quantized-mesh type tiles. The latter is more optimised for rendering. To process and create the tiles the *cesium-terrain-builder-docker* [2] utility is used. Afterwards, in order to serve the tiles, the *cesium-terrain-server* [3] utility is used. The *CesiumTerrainProvider* component will then be able to load the terrain from the URL provided by the *cesium-terrain-server* server.

Pointcloud-server preparation and usage : The process of visualising the point cloud starts with obtaining or downloading point cloud data. A standard format for this data is LAZ format, a compressed LiDAR Data Exchange file. The next step is to merge the input LAZ file or set of multiple files into a single LAS file, a format designed to interchange LiDAR point cloud data. Some open-source projects have been used to build the pipeline used by the solution. *LAStools* [5] is an open-source tool for LiDAR processing that permits this operation among others. Then, to convert a LAS file into 3D tiles, *Py3dtiles* [8] is used. Finally, a static 3D tiles server serves these tiles to view the point cloud using Cesium’s *Cesium3DTiles* function. The process has many steps, therefore an automated pipeline has been prepared, where the only interaction the application user has to make is to select the point cloud data folder that stores the data files to be served in LAZ format. Then, the process operations are automatically executed, as depicted in Fig. 9, and when the web interface is refreshed, the point cloud can be visualised. The options menu has functions to adjust the point cloud height to correct any deviations with the existing terrain and make a camera flight to it.

Fig. 9. Pipeline for the configuration and usage of point cloud data

Elevation-server preparation and usage : The elevation-server is used by the main API when a elevation profile is requested. This server has to be fed with elevation data in HGT format. HGT files are Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data files and can be downloaded from several sources. The

selected sequence of path points marked on the map of the user interface are sent to the API server to request an elevation profile. For each of the path points, the API requests the nearest reference point value of the altitude above sea level to the elevation-server. The result of the elevation profile query is represented in the CC web application through a Cesium *WallGraphics* component, and the height of the graphic corresponds to the elevation absolute values.

4 Performance evaluation

The performance of the multiple tasks and functionalities is affected by the number of records. How this size would affect the interaction of the user with the application or the feasibility of ingesting and presenting real-time data sources needs to be evaluated. In the following, we present the processing time required for two types of tasks, under a Ubuntu 18 8GB RAM, Intel Core i5-9400F CPU @ 2.90GHz.

4.1 Processing of First Responder locations

One of the features of the CC application is the initial flight described in section 3.4. To calculate the bounding box of the last positions received from the first responders deployed in an emergency, a custom API method has been implemented based on PostGIS. Another way to calculate the bounding box is to make use of one of the WPS functions provided by Geoserver. The processing times of both methods are compared.

The main factor that affects the processing time is the number of location records in the database and this is linked to: a) the rate at which data is sent by each first responder equipment, b) the duration of the data collection, and c) the total number of first responders sending location information. Tests have been performed for rates ranging from 20, 30, 60 and 300 seconds, data collections for 3 and 5 hours and 1, 5, 15 and 25 first responders.

Fig. 10. Response time comparison for different number of first responders (1, 5, 15, 25) and according to the number for records per FR, depending on the method: a) API. b) Geoserver.

Results show that the response time increases exponentially from 300 records per FR in the case of the API and from 540 records per FR in the case of Geoserver (Fig. 10). Focusing on scenarios with more records, the response of the API, in the worst case, is 2746% slower than Geoserver’s (the case of 1 record every minute during 5 hours with 25 first responders). Therefore, as future work, it is necessary to make the implementation of the API more efficient in order to improve scalability.

4.2 Processing of LiDAR point clouds

Processing multiple point cloud files to make them available for their consumption in the CC application requires some time. In order to understand the impact of the size and number of files to have the pointcloud-server ready to use by the Cesium component, we have measured the processing time for a set of point cloud files of different size and types. Fig. 11 shows the performance evaluation in processing time for partial steps (a) and the total process (b) before the server is up and running. Two different LiDAR open data sources have been compared to check possible differences due to the capturing method or the format: aerial (“LiDAR 2^a Cobertura” [7]) and terrestrial from mobile mapping (“2019 Mobile Mapping” [1]).

Fig. 11. a) Processing time of point cloud files sets of different size (in number of points) according to the time needed to convert different files into a single converted LAS file and the time needed to create 3D tiles. b) Total processing time needed to have the pointcloud-server ready, separating by the type of source.

We conclude that the relation between the processing time and the total size of the files to be combined (in number of point records or in file size) is linear. The number of files can be neglected and no significant differences have been found that could be associated with the point cloud data source.

5 Validation with First Responders

The proposed solution has been validated in two events simulating disaster management operational environments: a) the final project pilot held in the port of Valencia (Spain) where the solution was used in combination with other complementary solutions developed by project consortium partners under a larger project platform architecture and b) a session with a training centre for First Responders in Brunete (Spain).

5.1 Port environment exercise

The last training and pilot of the RESPOND-A project respectively took place on the 15th and 16th of February 2023 in the port of Valencia (Spain), Fig. 12. This final demonstration was a coordinated effort led by Fundación Valenciaport and the Valencia Local Police involving the project consortium as well as local organisations (Valencia Port Police, Firefighters, Mooring Services, Spanish Red Cross and Civil Protection). A total of approximately 150 participants were involved in the demonstration which simulated a traffic accident causing fire and oil spill - a type of hazard which can have very serious consequences on the personnel involved, critical infrastructures as well as the ecosystem.

The exercise consisted in managing the emergency to respond to a traffic accident between two trucks in the port surroundings causing fire and heavy smoke. As a consequence of the crash, the oil coming from one of the trucks fell into the sea. Therefore, the emergency response also had to contemplate the contention of the spilled oil floating on the water surface.

Fig. 12. a) Aerial view of the pilot site in Valencia Port, Spain (PNOA imagery [7]). b) One moment of the pilot exercise with the first responders deployed in the field.

The 3D GIS CC WebApp described in the present work was part of a joint deployment of a wide set of project components including health and environmental sensors, smart wearable sensors, augmented and virtual reality devices

and applications, reconnaissance and firefighting robots, drones, 5G connectivity and other Command and Control applications to enable communications and Common Operational Picture capabilities, increasing the situational awareness of First Responders in the field and those at the advanced command centre. The next key functions were specifically covered by the solution twice, during the first day as a training/rehearsal and during the second day as the pilot execution itself:

- The surroundings and 3D building models of the port area and the city were displayed.
- Weather alerts published by the Common Alerting Protocol were being received (non-existing at the moment of the pilot execution, and thus not reported).
- Bathymetry lines of the coastline were displayed.
- The real-time location and elevation of the drone were represented as it moved to obtain video images of the emergency area.
- The command centre operator draw the polygon of the current extension of the oil spill according to what the video from the drone was showing.
- The smart see-through glasses AR client application collected the real-time location of a first responder deployed in the field and that was displayed on the map at the CC centre.
- The smartphone AR client application collected the real-time location of a first responder deployed in the field, which was displayed on the map at the CC centre, and showed the extension of the oil spill through AR visualisation.

The exercise was satisfactory and all objectives were met and demonstrated.

5.2 Training Centre exercise

The session with a training centre for First Responders took place on the 9th and 10th of May 2023 in the VIGILES Institute, Brunete (Spain). VIGILES is a Civil Protection Institute for vocational education in civil protection and emergencies. The CC application was tested with over 30 people, including students and professionals. It was a two-day session.

During the first day session, all participants signed the consents, received a theoretical training and watched a demo of the tools (the CC WebApp and the AR Client applications) given by the researchers, and tested the installation of the software.

On the second day, exercises simulating real situations were performed in a properly prepared training camp. Next to the camp, there was a specific area where a big screen for the CC centre was installed, depicted in Fig. 13.

Tests consisted of three exercises with First Responder trainees divided into groups. The three exercises were repeated twice with different participants. The smartphone AR Client application installed in participants' devices tracked the location of First Responders and helped with searching tasks. One set of smart see-through glasses was used by one participant in each exercise. The exercises were:

Fig. 13. a) Aerial view of the training camp in Brunete, Spain (PNOA imagery [7]).
b) CC centre during training exercise.

- Standard search: Half of the group hid and the other half had to search. The CC centre monitored the situation while metrics were obtained.
- Guided search: Half of the group hid and the other half had to search. From the CC centre, there was direct communication by walkie-talkies to guide the search.
- Blind search with obstacles: Half of the group hid without location tracking and the other half had to search. When a searcher found a hidden "victim", they had to take the "victim" back to the CC centre, avoiding some dangerous areas drawn by the CC application operator. The rescuers were informed of the dangerous areas through the smartphone AR client.

At the end of the second day session, an extensive questionnaire assessing the used tools was filled out by the participants. The questionnaire had 23 questions about user experience, features, applicability and suggestions related to the CC WebApp. Fig. 14 shows a set of the most representative questions and the responses collected.

The following findings were extracted from the feedback of 31 questionnaire respondents:

- Regarding the professional future of the participants, 83% were focused on firefighting, 13% on search and rescue, and 4% on other tasks.
- The majority of them (70%) considered the CC web app is an easy-to-use tool and were interested in using it in the future.
- Over 85% of the people answered that 3D visualisation, 3D models and 3D terrain were crucial features for successful emergency response.
- Route calculation had the support of over 80% of the respondents.
- Although the creation of new elements had great acceptance, 11% of the participants answered that it was not easy to use.
- The information visualised in the CC web app was considered enough to give proper indications to First Responders in the field by 63%
- Most of them coincided with having real-time wind data would be a valuable add-on.

Fig. 14. Summary of evaluation results

- Most of them coincided with being able to send specific alerts from the CC centre to First Responders in the field would be a valuable add-on.

6 Discussion and future work

The evaluation of the performance tests demonstrated the quantitative impact of the amount of records and the frequency of sensor data captured when performing geospatial tasks and GIS server preparations such as the pointcloud-server in order to operate the web 3D GIS application. On one hand, it has been demonstrated that working on the scalability of the solution when developing custom functions in the API server is a must. To do so, the application and evaluation of geospatial stream processing frameworks is envisioned in the future. On the other hand, the incorporation of LiDAR pointcloud data from real-time sources must be studied as an interesting option for the future. With a linear relation between the total aggregated pointcloud size and the time needed to have the server restarted with new data, this would imply the delay would increase as more data files are received, but some alternatives could potentially be proposed and evaluated in order to manage the history of the files, according to time and space of the area covered.

The feedback from the port environment exercise was more limited than the one carried out in the training centre, due to the amount of technologies and tools that were tested at the same time.

It is worth mentioning that the validation with first responders in any of the exercises did not include the functionalities of point cloud visualisation, elevation profiles and ortophoto visualisation. In fact, these features were developed after

the validation exercises, partly because of the feedback and experience obtained in them.

7 Conclusions

This paper has described a CC web application based on 3D maps integrating novel and diverse geo-information sources for first responders in EMR. The description includes the functional applicability in disaster management by first responders operating the solution in a control centre, as well as the architectural and technical aspects that enable the integration and interaction of the end user with the tool.

The proposed components and overall structure of the 3D maps solution, which can be expanded for utilization in various CC contexts outside of emergency management, have been developed to interact with data coming from different heterogeneous sources and have been validated in relevant scenarios with positive feedback from professionals and trainees. These validation activities inspired to incorporate the latest innovations such as the inclusion of elevation profile calculation and point cloud visualisation, which were not developed (and thus were not tested by the end users) during validation activities. The solution acceptance by the trainees, without those features, was already high (90% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the 3D visualisation was helpful; 70% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they would like to use it in the future). This feedback, which comes from young adults used to new technologies that will become professional first responders in the near future, has been found positive and encourages the work on improving the performance of the solution, making the usage more intuitive and incorporating new functionality.

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References

1. b5m Infraestructura de Datos Espaciales de Gipuzkoa. <https://b5m.gipuzkoa.eus/web5000/es>, accessed: 2023-08-03
2. Cesium Terrain Builder. <https://github.com/tum-gis/cesium-terrain-builder-docker>, accessed: 2022-11-24
3. Cesium Terrain Server. <https://github.com/geo-data/cesium-terrain-server>, accessed: 2022-11-24
4. ImpOSM. <https://imposm.org/>, accessed: 2022-11-24
5. LAStools. <https://github.com/LAStools/LAStools>, accessed: 2023-08-03
6. Openstreetmap contributors. Retrieved from <http://planet.openstreetmap.org>, planet dump [Data file from: 2021-11-15]

7. Plan Nacional de Ortofotografía Aérea (PNOA) - Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN). <https://www.ign.es/web/ign/portal>, accessed: 2023-08-03
8. Py3dtiles. <https://gitlab.com/Oslandia/py3dtiles>, accessed: 2023-08-03
9. 3D Tiles. <https://www.ogc.org/standard/3dtiles/> (2022), accessed: 2023-07-03
10. Cesium JS, 3D geospatial visualization for the web. <https://cesium.com/platform/cesiumjs/> (2022), accessed: 2022-11-24
11. Abdalla, R.: Evaluation of spatial analysis application for urban emergency management. *SpringerPlus* **5** (12 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-3723-y>
12. Arregui, H., Irigoyen, E., Cejudo, I., Simonsen, S., Ribar, D., Kourtis, M., Spyridis, Y., Stathakarou, N., Batistatos, M.: An Augmented Reality Framework for First Responders: the RESPOND-A project approach. pp. 1–6 (12 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PACET56979.2022.9976376>
13. Bandrova, T., Zlatanova, S., Konečný, M.: Three-dimensional maps for disaster management. vol. I-4 (07 2012). <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsannals-I-4-245-2012>
14. Bennet, J.: *OpenStreetMap*. Packt Publishing Ltd (2010)
15. Cejudo, I., Irigoyen, E., Arregui, H., Loyo, E.: 3D Geospatial Data Management Architecture for Common Operational Picture Functionalities in Emergency Response. In: Grueau, C., Rodrigues, A., Ragia, L. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management, GISTAM 2023, Prague, Czech Republic, April 25-27, 2023*. pp. 48–59. SCITEPRESS (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011837800003473>, <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011837800003473>
16. Dijkstra, E.W.: A note on two problems in connexion with graphs. *Numerische mathematik* **1**(1), 269–271 (1959)
17. Ezquerro, P., Bru, G., Galindo, I., Monserrat, O., García-Davalillo, J., Sánchez, N., Montoya, I., Palamà, R., Mateos, R., Pérez-López, R., González-Alonso, E., Grandin, R., Guardiola-Albert, C., López-Vinielles, J., Fernández-Merodo, J., Herrera, G., Béjar-Pizarro, M.: Analysis of SAR-derived products to support emergency management during volcanic crisis: La Palma case study. *Remote Sensing of Environment* **295**, 113668 (2023). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113668>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0034425723002195>
18. Gao, X., Zhang, J., Zou, R., Li, J., Cao, Z.: Multi-user collaborative virtual emergency drill system for urban road emergencies. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* **X-3/W2-2022**, 9–15 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-annals-X-3-W2-2022-9-2022>, <https://www.isprs-ann-photogramm-remote-sens-spatial-inf-sci.net/X-3-W2-2022/9/2022/>
19. Hart, P., Nilsson, N., Raphael, B.: A formal basis for the heuristic determination of minimum cost paths. *IEEE Transactions on Systems Science and Cybernetics* **4**(2), 100–107 (1968). <https://doi.org/10.1109/tssc.1968.300136>, <https://doi.org/10.1109/tssc.1968.300136>
20. Hong, J.H., Lu, Y.H., Chen, C.H.: The use of CCTV in the emergency response: A 3D GIS perspective. *The International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* **42**, 19–25 (2019)
21. Iacovella, S.: *GeoServer Beginner’s Guide: Share Geospatial Data Using Open Source Standards*. Packt Publishing Ltd (2017)
22. Jagusiak, B., Pokorski, G.: Application of transport security system symbology for emergency mass notification systems. *Transport Problems: an International Scientific Journal* **17**(3) (2022)

23. Jutz, S., Milagro-Pérez, M.: Copernicus: the European Earth Observation programme. *Revista de Teledetección* (56), V–XI (2020)
24. Kolawole, O., Hunukumbure, M.: A Drone-based 3D Localization Solution for Emergency Services. In: ICC 2022-IEEE International Conference on Communications. pp. 1–6. IEEE (2022)
25. Li, B., Wu, J., Pan, M., Huang, J.: Application of 3D WebGIS and real-time technique in earthquake information publishing and visualization. *Earthquake Science* **28**, 223–231 (06 2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11589-015-0124-1>
26. Momjian, B.: PostgreSQL: Introduction and Concepts. Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., USA (2001)
27. Mysiris, P., Doulamis, N., Doulamis, A., Sourlas, V., Amditis, A.: Pervasive 3D Reconstruction to Identify Hidden 3D Survival Spaces for Search and Rescue Management. In: 2018 IEEE 16th Intl Conf on Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing, 16th Intl Conf on Pervasive Intelligence and Computing, 4th Intl Conf on Big Data Intelligence and Computing and Cyber Science and Technology Congress. pp. 808–813 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/DASC/PiCom/DataCom/CyberSciTec.2018.00-25>
28. Raible, M.: The JHipster Mini-Book. Lulu.com (2016)
29. Shah, S.A., Seker, D.Z., Hameed, S., Draheim, D.: The rising role of big data analytics and IoT in disaster management: Recent advances, taxonomy and prospects. *IEEE Access* **7**, 54595–54614 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2913340>
30. Tan, Y., Liang, Y., Zhu, J.: CityGML in the Integration of BIM and the GIS: Challenges and Opportunities. *Buildings* **13**(7) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13071758>, <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/13/7/1758>
31. Verykokou, S., Ioannidis, C., Athanasiou, G., Doulamis, N., Amditis, A.: 3D reconstruction of disaster scenes for urban search and rescue. *Multimedia Tools and Applications* **77** (04 2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-017-5450-y>
32. Walls, C.: *Spring Boot in Action*. Manning Publications Co., USA, 1st edn. (2016)
33. Zlatanova, S.: SH for emergency response: the 3D challenges (06 2008)
34. Zlatanova, S., Oosterom, P., Verbree, E.: 3D technology for improving disaster management: Geo-dbms and positioning. *Proceedings of The IEEE - PIEEE* (07 2004)